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THE VOCABULARY OF SCIENTIFIC WORKS IN THE 13th-16th CENTURIES TURKIC LANGUAGES

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Abstract

One of the distinguished styles in terms of functionality of literary language is scientific style. Scientific style has a long history in Turkic languages. Formulation of scientific style occurs in the highest stage of evolution of literary language. In this regard formation history of scientific styles in Turkic languages, in fact, reflects also the history of Turkic literary languages. Thus style differentiation informs about enhancing of expressing capabilities in the diversification of the language. The scientific style, which is one of the styles of language having a different position in terms of functionality, has its own internal laws. This regularity is mostly related to the lexical layer of the language. Thus, when clarifying the characteristics of the scientific style, first of all, it's taken into account that it's a term. The term characterizes the scientific style as a unit of language vocabulary and has functionality in a limited range. From the analysis of the lexical stock of the scientific style in the XIII-XIV centuries, it is clear that native terms are the core of the scientific style in the Turkic languages. Their percentage of usage varies from one field to another, and mainly in Turks it is possible to determine with it which sciences have a more ancient history. Native terminology as a part of the people's language is a special language layer with deep roots, having comprehensive usability and forming on the basis of different word-formation constructions.

Keywords: term, scientific style, vocabulary, loanwords, Turkic languages, Chagatai, Azerbaijanian, Turkish, Kipchak, Karakhani.

Introduction

The styles that manifested using potential of language in society in different forms, at the same time, reflect the developmental perspectives of language in the form of various layers. As B. de Courtenay says, "Language is a complex category potentially existing and a continuously repeating process". The language units that are part of this dynamic and continuous complex process are realized differently within a specific sphere and environment. Distinctive realization and manifestation cause to internal divisions in language. In fact, this internal division occurs according to the principle of being used the language in the speech process. As a result, the style of using language is formed on the basis of differences in the process of thinking and comprehension in a specific language environment. Although this style manifesting in accordance with the general rules of language, it differs from other communicative levels of language by its conformity to specific norms and its specific frameworks of usage.

F.de Saussure writes pointing out the difference between language and speech: "The study of language activity is divided into two parts: the first of them is basic, its basis is language, it doesn't have essentially a social character and doesn't depend on the individuality. The second is secondary, speech activity is related to individuality, in other words, speech is related to speaking. Both subjects are closely related (Saussure, p.28). The individuality that the author discusses in the connection between language and speech coincides with the concept of style. It is intended to distinguish the individual and normative style from each other. Although both manifest in fact purely in the process of speech, a normative style is an act of language that follows the norms required at a concrete level of language. Although such norms are expected in the individual style itself, it appears as an individual approach and a unique speech variant of the language user. In fact, this is a historical process occurring in the language. Thus, at the same time, the most correct and right of the existing variants of speech in the language, or the most

widely used, gradually becomes the norm. In the process of development, the individual style becomes a part of the normative style and acquires the right of the norm. Sometimes this process does not happen and this manifests itself as a deviation from a norm. "Within a centralized literary language, separate functional styles are formed in accordance with the position of creating of appropriate language standards. Each style begins to stand out with its internal normality" (Huseynzade, p.77).

Written works mainly play a role of source in reviving the linguistic landscape of a concrete historical period. In researches from the point of view of language history in modern Azerbaijani linguistics, such works are mainly distinguished from the fictional style examples. Looking at the linguistic landscape of the Middle Ages on the basis of the possibilities of the solemn, pathetic classical fictional style, in fact, reflects an incomplete approach to the language situation of that period. It is true that the lack of works on certain stages of development of the Turkic languages, after the Orkhon-Yenisei monuments and Uyghur texts, literary writings examples related to Khaganian Turkic, and then the existence of fictional works created only by poets in Turkic, has brought the tradition of studying the history of literary language in linguistics on the basis of fictional style. However, there are enough works related to the scientific style among the works that reflect the separate language features at different stages of the historical development of the Turkic languages. This allows us to say that the scientific style in the Turkic languages has a centuries-old history of development.

The scientific style and use of terms in scientific works

The scientific style, which is one of the styles of language having a different position in terms of functionality, has its own internal laws. This regularity is mostly related to the lexical layer of the language. Thus, when clarifying the characteristics of the scientific style, first of all, it's taken into account that it's a term. The term characterizes the scientific style as a unit of vocabulary of language and has functionality in a limited range. Terms being the lexical category are distinguished from other language units by their definitive function. Every word in a language can have a nominative function, but definiteness characterizes the word and gives it the character of a term. S. A. Sadigova writes: "The term doesn't name a notion as an ordinary word, the notion is attached to the term, i.e. the meaning of the term is its determination. If the determination is unknown, the term is also unknown. So, the term doesn't name the notion as an ordinary word, the notion realizes through it" (Sadigova, p. 16).

In the Turkic-language scientific works of the 13th-16th centuries, numerous linguistic units called terms, historically named "istilah" have been used. The diversity of topics and wide spectrum of scientific works of the period provide a great variety of terminological lexicon. Numerous terms were reflected related to both secular and religious sciences in the works written during this period "Muyassiratul-ulum", "Mizanul-evzan", "Ad durratul-mudiyya fil-lugatit-

turkiye", "Tohfatul-Ahavan", "Kitabul-Bahriya", "Khulasa", "Nahjul-Faradis", "Adviyya i-Mufrada", "Tarihi-Ali-Osman", "Muntahabi-Shifa" and so on. For example: başcuğaz (boil), balhiyya (a disease manifested itself by boils and tumors), bez (swab), bıçku, sil (tuberculosis), sivilcü (acne), tumağu (flu), tamur (nosebleed), tavuk karağusu (eye disease), çintiyana (healing herb), demürçiler körüğü tuzu (a type of salt used in medicine), giciyik (allergic pruritus), arazvarı/arazbar (one of the ancient mughams of classical Turkish music), bahri-jadid (the later-created bahr that is shown in the third circle in Ajam arud, but not available in Arabic arud), buday-buday (according to Navai, it is one of the types of songs in Uzbeks and does not similar to any meter), çenge (a song sung by Turks when taking the bride at weddings), koşuk (a song written in the meter of ramali-murabbai-mahzuf), ozan, ozmaq (according to Navai, it is a song sung by poets playing the komuz), urğuştək (method of composing koshuks), yüzükci, dağ erüğü, demregü, yalavaç, ferışteler, uçmak, tamu, gün balkımağı, ay yıldırması, demür, bakır, kalay, erziz, kömür, kılıç, süñü, alamı- eşxas (name of persons), bina-i nevi-mechul (passive voice), cemi-müntahab (the second person plural), emri-ğayib (the third person singular of the imperative mood), edatı-liyakat, ismi-tafzil, ismi-taşğir, iştiqaq, izafeti-acemiyye, izafeti- beyaniyye, ismi-zaman, gövheri- şeb-çıraç (ruby shining at night), kulami, fufuli (type of pearl), haceri-lubni (medicinal stone, used in eye diseases), mişmiş (yellow ruby), mukantarat (an astronomical instrument), mıntkatul-buruc, ilmul- hendese, ilmul-misaha, ilmur-riyaka, ilmul-ukudil-ebniye ets. These terms that given have different characteristics thematically, in terms of origin and method of formation.

The using positions of language units in different fields of science, which are divided into national and borrowed terms by origin, are also different. Looking at the terminological landscape of the period, it seems that both ancient Turkic lexical layer and terms of Arabic and Persian origin predominate in scientific works. The multiplicity of borrowed terms in the religious and human sciences is due to both the specific features of these science fields and the formation of these fields of science on the basis of the Arabic language. Although the majority of words of Turkic origin in medicine are related to the development of science over traditional folk medicine, the existence of borrowed words from different languages is due to the diversity of scientific sources.

The dominance of Arabic and Persian language of science in the region in the 9th-13th centuries caused Turkish authors to write their works in this language. Ibn Sina, Farabi, H.Tiflisi, N.Tusi, N.Nakhchivani, S.Al-Bardai, S.Urmavi, A.Maraghayi etc. hundreds of Turkish thinkers were accepted as representatives of Arabic and Persian language of science, and their works were propagated under the common name of Islamic science. However, their works in Arabic and Persian were the main sources of the Turkic scientific style. Thus, the first scientific works written in Turkic from the XIV century were, in fact, the translations and interpretations of works written in other languages by

great thinkers and scientists who lived in this region in the IX-XIII centuries. While researching the history of translated works, M. Naghisoylu comes to the conclusion that “Translated literature in Azerbaijan has directly connected with the development of native language literature, has stepped with it, or rather spread and formed as one of its branches. That is why the translated literature reached its highest stage of development in the 15th-16th centuries” (Naghisoylu, p. 16-17). In parallel with this process, such examples have been replaced by original author's works. All these factors also influenced the formation of the system of scientific style norms, and through the translation works foreign constructions, language units have entered the language. This aspect showed itself mostly in the terminological lexicon. When looking through scientific works of the XIII-XVI centuries, the diversity of terminological lexicon attracts the attention. In scientific works of the period, along with terms of Turkic origin such as yulduz, tumağu, tamar, koşuk, ad, ağac, bulut, çevkan, çiy, bunar, demür, gögüz, kırлагuc, kirağu, bağa yarpağı, burçak, dağlağı, öyken, sayruluk, ozmaq, Arabic origin such as batnulhut (phases of the month), benatun-naş (name of star), cibal (mountains), ıtriful, hudad, devali, şatru-ğıbb, sui-mizac, Persian origin such as felencemüşk, hunni-siyavuşan (medicine made from a type of tree), ladan (medicinal ointment made from a healing herb), mumruğan, reg- bend (bandage, tampon), Greek origin such as fuluniya, asarun, ayaric, malihulya, kimmun, sakmuniya, sisenber, masarika, zusenteriya, ziyanitis, baselik, kıstındus, hybrid language units such as masarika tamarı, toxmekan yaprağının suyu (p+t), devali tamarı (a+t), namazboz (p+t), tendürüstlik (p+t), hokka süñüğü (a+t) were used and it is possible to divide the terminological lexicon into three parts according to their origin:

- National terms
- Borrowed terms
- Hybrid terms

It is clear from the research that the frequency of use of national words and borrowings is not the same in all periods in scientific works. In the period when the first Turkic-language works were written while it is observed that the terms such as uçmak, tamu, gün balkımağı, ay yıldırması, ilduz (astronomy), yuqaruğı, yaku, aşığağı, demregü, dağlağı (medicine), turğay, delüce toğan, üğü have been dominated by parallels with the ancient Turkic lexicon, in 15th-16th centuries the terms of Arabic origin such as dahilî-urük (malaria, which causes inflammation of the arteries), azā, baraş (name of the disease), batun-ı dimağ (inside the brain), daireyi- irtifa; hundreds of terms of Persian origin such as bāselik (carotid), beladı-kimmun, nergis, mignatis, lodra (unit of weight), dolfin (dolphin), nilüfer, salyar kimi yunan; terengubin, düser (a tax levied on both the buyer and the seller), gireh (unit of length), yekser (one-sided tax), menn (unit of measurement of silk), baras (vitiligo), derya, nakare, bazu, gülefsar are reflected in scientific works.

At some points, national and borrowed words are used in parallel: beg börki (t.)- şahtere (p.); deñiz köpüğü (t.)- kef-ı-derya (p.)- zebedül-bahr (a.); sayruluk

(t.)- derd (p.)- illet (a.) renc (p.); zaymuran (a.)- şahperüm (p.) (bitki adı); zikun-nefes (a.)-nefes tarlığı (t.), zūsentāriyā (y.)- allahumme erham (a.); göyündürme (t.)- ekile (a.)-höre (p.) (skin disease); yürek oynaması- hafakān(a.); öyke-opke -ciger(p.) etc.;

The frequency of usage of borrowings in the field of science is also different. For example, let's look at an extract from the work “Khulaseyi-Tibb” by the chief surgeon Masud, who lived in the 15th century: “Evvel baş tamarı kim aña yāfūh derler andan kan alınursa aña menfaat baş ağrısın giderür ve göz kanın keser, ikinci aluñ tamarı kim aña cebhe derler menfaat qulaq qurulduşın açar ve göz qanın keser ve baş ceşginmesini giderür, üçüncü kaş yanında olur aña irkul- hacıbeyn derler... dördüncü eñse tamarı kim aña halifur-resir derler...beşinci tuluñ tamarı kim aña ırkuş-şakkika derler... altıncı kulak ardındağı tamara halful-lāzun dërler (Uçar, 59a).

As can be seen, the sentence structure and the manner of expression in the work are very simple, most of the words used are of Turkic origin. However, the author definitely gives equivalent to the names of the veins and emphasizes their importance. Other words given by the author as doublet terms are as follows: “Göz bigāri tamarı-mākul-ayn; burun tamarı- ırkul-enf; dutuk içinde iki tamar- ırkuş-şefateyn; dil altındağı iki tamar- ırkul-lisan; boyunda iki tamar- veddāçeyn;sağ kolda baş tamarı- kīfāl; gevde tamarı- ekhel; baş barmaq tamarı- habluz-zira; 17-ci tamar- ekhel tamarı altında olur- bāselik; 18-ci tamar- baselik tamarı altında olur- useylem”(Uçar,59b).

A. Navai who lived in the same century, his work “Mizanul-Evzan” is one of the valuable sources on the science of aruz-literature. When you look at the borrowings in his language, the features that are different from the above attracts the attention: “Amma malu bolsun kim Aruz fennide nazm evzanı usulıning binasın üç rükngə koyuqturlar kim alarnı “sebeb” ve “veted” ve “fasıla” dipdürler. Sebeb ikki nevdir. Sebebi hafif ve ol lafızdır mustemil bir müteharrik ve bir sakinga andak kim: mey ve nel ve gül(1) ve sebbi- sakil... Veted dağı ikki kısımdur... Fasıla dağı iki nevdir (Navai, p.13)

It is clear from this extract from “Mizanul-Evzan”, one of the most important works on the theory of literature of its time that the language of the work is as heavy as the aruz rhythm itself, and is rich in Arabic and Persian words and expressions. If we look at the statistical index of the terms used in the work, we see that out of 579 aruz terms, only about 10 terms are of Turkic origin, and these are mainly the names of Turkic types of poetry.

One of the first Ottoman historians, Ashik Pashazade, who lived in the 15th century, wrote “Tavarikh-ali-Osman” is distinguished from other scientific sources of his time in its simple Turkic. Let's look at the part about Uzun Hasan in the 150th chapter of the work: “Uzun Hasan Bayındur Han neslindendir ve hem ol Uzun Hasandur kim Tarhan beg oğlını sıdı ve dahı Çagataydan Ebu Said ısıdı” (Paşazade,p.457). “Kaçan kim Koylıhisarı feth idicek Erzincan tarafına yürüdü bu tarafdandır Uzun Hasan dahı kendü anasını ve Çimişkezek begi Şeyh Kürt Hasanı anasına qoşup Sultan Muhammed Hana göndürdü ilçilige... Be-gayet

yahşı armagan getürdi. Padişah dahı armaganların aldı. Be-gayet eyü tazimler itdi. Ve Uzun Hasan anası Sara Hatunı ana idindi.”(Paşazade, p.434). In the text borrowings such as “ve, həm, nəsl, fəth, dahı, be-gayet, padişah, tazim, taraf” have been used.

Conclusion.

It is clear from the research that this process observed in the works belonging to different scientific directions of the same period is in fact related to the development features of each field of science. The examples given mainly cover the linguistic facts of Ottoman Turkic and Chagatai Turkic. Both languages have been strongly influenced by Persian and Arabic since the 15th century. In fact, this is due to the difficulty in expressing new concepts with the expansion of the functionality of both Turkic languages. Thus, the formation features of language units of the scientific style arise both in relation to the language's own spectrum of communication and the scope of the field of science to which the work belongs.

When looking through the lexical stock of works belonging to scientific style in the Turkic languages of the 13th-16th centuries, we can see that the terms were formed in different ways. Such terms either express new concepts by undergoing lexical-semantic changes,

or form by adding suffixes to words to express new concepts, or become a means of expressing a complex concept combining two words.

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